

SPACE ASTROMETRY :

GRID OPTIMIZATION AND DOUBLE-STAR DETECTION

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The problem of double-star detection and its impact on grid optimization has been dealt with in three previous notes (Lindegren 77-06-15, 78-02-01 and 78-03-10) and summarized in a contribution to the Padova Colloquium in June 1978. The present note summarizes very briefly some results of new computations, using a more complete instrument model and a slightly different angle of attack.

Main emphasis is put on a reasonable modelling of the wavelength dependent sensitivity and MTF of the telescope plus detector, and on the simulation of photon counts and subsequent computation of the multidimensional likelihood function for the entire history of observation of a particular star or system of stars.

The original aim was in fact to generate a set of stars and star systems, representative of an actual observing program, simulate the resulting photon counts and apply routines for estimating the parameters (including magnitudes, separations and position angles as well as the positions, proper motions and parallaxes of the primary stars or centres of gravity), and finally to collect the statistics of errors, misdetections, etc for the set.

The basic estimation routines for such an enterprise have been worked out and seem to function very well, except that the computing time on the available computer (Univac 1100) turned out to be prohibitive (about one hour per star).

Because of this, I have performed only a much simplified study of about 20 "typical" double stars, to assess their detectability and the statistical errors to be expected if they escape detection. Various theoretical and semi-empirical scaling laws have been employed to extend the results to most cases of practical interest.

These results were obtained for a specific baseline instrument, to be defined below. However, some calculations of the single-star accuracy as function of certain design parameters have been performed as well, to see the effects of an increased obscuration of the entrance pupil, of a lower sampling rate, etc.

1. Basic assumptions and model parameters

1.1. Stellar fluxes: these are defined by the apparent visual magnitude V and colour $C = (B-V)_0$. No reddening is assumed. The adopted fluxes are shown in Fig. 1.

1.2. Scanning law: uniform revolving scanning with $\zeta = 0.6 \text{ rad} = 34.377^\circ$ and $K = 7.85398$. Note that K was deliberately chosen an irrational number to avoid repetition of scanning geometry from one year to another. $R = 10$ and about 80 % time efficiency means that the average observing time per star per scan is about 8 sec (for a total of 100 000 stars), which is assumed for all stars independent of magnitude.

1.3. Instrument: the two entrance pupils have identical shape, i.e. half-circular (diameter 0.25 m) with a half-circular obstruction (diameter 0.44×0.25 m). It is essentially aberration-free, i.e. the effective MTF can be computed from the entrance pupil diffraction alone. The total transmission of the instrument is shown in Fig. 2. This curve $T(\lambda)$ does not include the factors $(1 - 0.44^2)$ and $\delta = r/s$ from respectively the entrance pupil obstruction and the average grid obstruction.

The grid is monodimensional with slits normal to the nominal scanning direction; it is defined by the grid period s and the ratio of clear band width to the period, $\delta = r/s$. It will be shown that the optimum grid for the baseline instrument is $s = 1''2$ and $\delta = 0.23$, which is always assumed. The FOV is $0.9 \times 1.2^\circ$.

The photocathode quantum efficiency is shown in Fig. 3. The photon counts are sampled at a frequency of 2 kHz, with no loss of counts; the entire count record is assumed to be available for analysis (no data compression).

The background current is $b = 5 + 800\delta$ Hz (counts/sec). This includes a dark current of 5 Hz and a background intensity in the IFOV corresponding to one star of magnitude $B = 12.3$ in the IFOV or 23 stars of $B = 15$ per 10^{-4} square degree (IFOV $\phi 30''$).

1.4. Geometry of scans. In order to save computing time, all calculations were made for a star (single or double) at ecliptical coordinates $(\lambda, \beta) = (1, 0.5)$ rad. With 2.5 years of revolving scanning this point on the sky is scanned 33 times at 15 different epochs. The "step 3 improvement factors" for $\lambda, \beta, \mu_\lambda, \mu_\beta, \bar{\omega}$ are respectively 0.334, 0.223, 0.467, 0.295, 0.329, which are about 30% greater than the sky averages (for $\zeta = 36^\circ$) computed by ACM. This shows that our particular choice of position (λ, β) is rather on the pessimistic side.

2. Grid optimization

The optimum grid parameters s and δ were found as follows. The mean error of the one-dimensional position (along the scan) of a single star or of the primary or centre of gravity of a double star, as obtained from a "typical" 8 sec record of counts (corresponding to an average scan), is computed as outlined in my note 77-06-15 (Appendix). Thus, possible contributions from jitter are neglected. Tables 1-3 give the resulting mean error as function of s and δ for single $V = 10$ stars of different colours. Maximum accuracy would be obtained with $s \approx 0''7$ and $\delta \approx 0.35$, but such a grid would be unsuitable for observing double stars. Thus, we must turn to the secondary maximum near $s = 1''2$ and $\delta = 0.23$. Since the precise location of the maximum depends on the colour of the star, a compromise must be found. Allowing at most 5% loss of accuracy, we should stay within the 95% contours shown in the tables.

The corresponding accuracy maps for a double star are given in Tables 4-6.

It is found that the point $s = 1''20$, $\delta = 0.23$ is within the 95% contours in all six cases and is thus an acceptable compromise.

With these parameters and the baseline instrument described above it is found that the following analytical approximations can be used for the average photoelectron rate $i(V, C)$ due to a star of magnitude V and colour C , and for the mean error $\sigma(V, C, T, b)$ of a position in the grid frame due to photoelectron noise only:

$$i(V, C) = \text{dex}\{-0.4(V - 9)\} \text{ dex}\{2.91 + 0.92/(1.5 + C)\} \quad \text{Hz}, \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma^2(V, C, T, b) = \frac{0.115}{T \cdot i(V, C)} \left\{ 1 + 0.92 \frac{b}{i(V, C)} \right\} (1 - 0.32 C + 0.64 C^2) \quad \text{arcsec}^2, \quad (2)$$

where T is the total time (in sec) spent on the star and b is the background current. In all our calculations $T = 8$ sec per scan and $b = 189$ Hz; thus, for a

V = 9 star we have Table 7:

C = B-V	i(9, C)	$\sigma(9, C, 8^S, 189 \text{ Hz})$
0.0	3340 Hz	2.1 marcsec
0.5	2340 Hz	2.6 marcsec
1.0	1900 Hz	2.9 marcsec

The "mean error per scan" of star abscissas are roughly estimated by:

$$\sigma_{\text{absc}} = 1.3 (\sigma^2 + \langle \sigma^2 \rangle)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

(derived from the numerical solutions in my note 77-04-15), where σ is the m.e. from (2) and $\langle \sigma^2 \rangle$ the corresponding average variance within the scan. If all stars have the same magnitude B = 9 we find $\sigma_{\text{absc}} = 3.9$ marcsec, with on the average 228 sec accumulated observing time per star per year. The corresponding figure used in the Phase A Report (see my note 78-04-08) is $4.5 \times (612/228)^{1/2} = 7.4$ marcsec. This indicates that, as far as photon noise is the limiting factor, there is room for some improvement in the final results compared with the figures given in the Phase A Report.

3. Deviations from the baseline

If a bialkali photocathode is used instead of the baseline S20, there is a slight loss of accuracy due to the decreased number of photoelectrons (Fig. 2, dashed line)

Colour C	0.0	0.5	1.0	(bialkali)
Relative m.e.	1.02	1.04	1.13	

On the other hand, some improvement is possible by using UV transparent relay optics (Fig. 3, dashed curve), together with the S20 cathode:

Colour C	0.0	0.5	1.0	(quartz optics)
Relative m.e.	0.84	0.93	0.99	

For a possible new optical design it may be of interest to increase the secondary mirror obstruction factor η over its present value 0.44. The effects on the m.e. are as follows:

η	0.40	0.44	0.50	0.60	(obstruction ratio)
Relative m.e.	0.92	1.00	1.16	1.58	

Finally, the lowest possible sampling rate should of course be used for several reasons:

Sampling frequency	2000	1500	1000	800	600 Hz
Relative m.e.	1.00	1.01	1.04	1.08	1.16

4. Maximum-likelihood estimation of astrometric parameters and double-star parameters

Given the complete record of counts $\{n_j\}$ for a particular star (single or multiple) over the entire period of observation (2.5 years), and assuming that the scans have been at least preliminarily calibrated (e.g. the scan zero points determined), it is very easy to write down the complete expression for the logarithm of the likelihood as function of all relevant parameters:

$$\ln \text{lik} = \text{const.} + L(\underline{a}, V_1, C_1, V_2, C_2, \rho, \theta, b_j, \dots), \quad (4)$$

where $\underline{a}$ is the (5x1) vector containing the astrometric parameters, V_k, C_k are the magnitude and colour of the k:th star ($k = 1, 2$), ρ and θ are the separation and position angle of the double star, and b_j is the background level for the observations in the j:th scan. The problem is to find the absolute maximum of (4).

The approach taken here is to make a trial assumption on $C_1, C_2, V_2 - V_1, \rho$, and θ , and then make a solution for the other parameters. (This means that the problem is essentially reduced to the same level as with the single-star hypothesis.) Such trial solutions can be obtained for a sequence of magnitude differences $V_2 - V_1$ (increasing from 0) in order to maximize L with respect to this parameter as well. If C_1 and C_2 are regarded as known, we then have only two parameters left, viz. ρ and θ , i.e. the relative position of the secondary with respect to the primary.

This results in a likelihood map like in Fig. 4, in which the global maximum must be located. The corresponding solution for $\underline{a}$ is then adopted if the likelihood ratio is sufficient.

The likelihood ratio can be predicted for various configurations of stars (Fig. 5), yielding an indication of which cases are probably detectable. The expected root-mean-square parallax errors for borderline cases are shown in Fig. 6; these are generally much less than the random errors given e.g. in the Phase A Report. Since such cases are anyway not very frequent, the conclusion is that double stars have insignificant effects on the overall accuracy of astrometric results, but may require an even more laborious data processing technique than we have thought.

Fig. 1. Smoothed monochromatic fluxes of unreddened mainsequence stars (visual magnitude $V = 0$) as function of wavelength and colour $C = (B-V)_0$. Compiled from data from Willstrop (1964), Schmidt-Kaler (1965), O'Connell (1973) and Jamar *et al.* (1976). Dashed curves indicate extrapolated fluxes.

Fig. 2. Total transmission of instrument (Mirrors, grid support, relay optics, IDT window). The baseline instrument is supposed to have ordinary glass relay optics (solid line); an option with UV transparent optics is admitted (dashed line).

Fig. 3. Photocathode quantum efficiency. S20 is the baseline (solid line), but bialkali (dashed line) may be considered, e.g. in order to reduce chromaticity effects.

Fig. 4. Example of likelihood map for the location of a secondary star. The true situation is depicted in the top figure. The magnitudes of the components are $B_1 = 10.5$ and $B_2 = 11.5$, colours $C_1 = C_2 = 0.5$, separation $\rho = 0''.700$ and position angle $\theta = 2.5$ rad. The position of the system is $(\lambda, \beta) = (1, 0.5)$ rad. During 2.5 years of revolving scanning ($\zeta = 0.6$ rad) the system is observed in 33 scans at 15 different epochs, and for 8 seconds in each scan. Randomized photon counts were then simulated and the likelihood map (bottom) computed. Four local maxima were located; the highest maximum (log likelihood = 1441) coincides with the true position of the secondary within 3-4 milliarcsec. The relative log likelihood is strictly zero in the shaded area, meaning that the fit can only be worse by assuming the presence of a secondary there, however faint.

Fig. 5. Double-star detectability. The curves show the characteristics of double stars (separation, blue-magnitude difference, and primary magnitude B_1) for which the non-centrality parameter (averaged over position angles θ) is $\Lambda = 80$. This means that cases above the curves are almost surely detected even with a likelihood-ratio criterion for which the probability of false detection is negligible (assuming, of course, that $-2\ln(\text{likelihood ratio})$ is in fact χ^2 distributed).

Fig. 6. Rms parallax error (milliarcsec), as function of separation and primary magnitude B_1 , for the limiting cases of $\Lambda = 80$, i.e. for the magnitude differences ΔB shown in Fig. 5.

Table 1. Accuracy as function of grid parameters [grid period and (width of clear bands)/(grid period)]. The table gives σ^{-1} in arcsec $^{-1}$, rounded to nearest integer, for an 8 sec observation of a single star of magnitude V = 10 and colour C = 0. The contour shows the regions where the accuracy is > 95 % of the accuracy at the secondary maximum.

GRID PER. (")	DELTA															
	.08	.11	.14	.17	.20	.23	.26	.29	.32	.35	.38	.41	.44	.47	.50	.53
.40	80	93	104	113	120	126	131	134	136	138	138	137	135	133	129	125
.42	104	121	135	146	156	163	169	174	177	178	179	178	175	172	167	162
.44	126	147	164	178	189	199	206	212	215	217	217	216	213	209	204	197
.46	146	170	190	206	220	231	239	245	249	252	252	250	247	242	236	228
.48	163	190	211	230	244	256	266	273	277	280	280	278	275	269	262	253
.50	176	205	229	248	264	277	287	295	300	302	303	304	297	291	283	273
.52	186	217	242	262	279	293	303	311	316	319	319	317	313	307	299	288
.54	193	225	250	272	289	303	314	322	328	331	331	329	324	318	309	299
.56	197	230	256	278	296	310	322	330	335	338	338	336	331	325	316	305
.58	200	233	260	282	300	315	326	334	340	342	343	340	336	329	320	309
.60	201	234	261	283	301	316	327	336	341	344	344	342	337	330	321	310
.62	201	234	261	283	301	316	327	335	341	344	344	342	337	330	321	310
.64	199	232	259	281	299	314	325	333	339	342	342	340	335	328	319	309
.66	197	229	256	278	296	310	321	330	335	338	338	336	332	325	316	306
.68	194	226	252	273	291	306	317	325	331	334	334	332	328	321	313	302
.70	191	222	248	269	286	301	312	320	325	328	329	327	323	317	308	298
.72	188	218	244	264	282	295	306	314	320	323	323	322	318	312	304	294
.74	185	215	240	260	277	291	301	309	314	317	318	316	312	307	299	290
.76	183	213	237	257	273	287	297	304	309	312	312	311	307	302	294	285
.78	182	212	236	255	271	284	293	300	305	307	307	306	302	297	290	281
.80	183	212	235	254	270	282	291	297	301	303	303	301	297	292	285	277
.82	184	213	236	255	270	281	289	295	298	299	299	297	293	288	281	274
.84	186	215	238	257	271	281	288	293	296	296	295	293	289	284	278	270
.86	189	219	242	259	273	282	289	293	294	294	292	289	285	280	274	268
.88	193	223	245	263	276	284	290	293	293	292	290	286	282	277	271	265
.90	197	227	250	267	279	287	292	294	293	291	288	284	279	274	269	263
.92	201	232	254	271	283	290	294	295	293	290	286	282	276	271	266	261
.94	205	236	259	275	286	293	295	294	290	285	280	274	269	264	259	
.96	209	240	263	279	290	295	298	294	290	284	278	272	267	262	257	
.98	213	244	267	283	294	299	301	299	295	290	283	277	271	265	260	256
1.00	216	247	270	286	297	302	303	301	296	290	283	276	269	264	259	255
1.02	218	250	273	289	299	304	305	302	299	290	282	275	268	263	258	254
1.04	220	252	275	291	301	306	306	303	297	290	282	275	268	262	257	253
1.06	222	254	277	293	303	307	307	304	298	290	282	274	267	261	256	253
1.08	223	255	279	294	304	308	308	304	298	291	282	274	267	261	256	253
1.10	224	256	280	295	305	309	309	305	299	291	282	274	267	261	256	252
1.12	225	257	280	296	305	309	309	305	299	291	283	274	267	261	256	253
1.14	226	258	281	296	306	310	309	305	299	291	283	275	267	261	257	253
1.16	226	258	281	297	306	310	309	305	299	292	283	275	268	262	257	253
1.18	227	259	282	297	306	310	309	305	299	292	284	276	269	263	258	254
1.20	227	259	282	297	306	309	309	305	299	292	285	277	270	264	259	255
1.22	228	260	282	297	306	309	309	305	299	293	285	278	271	265	260	256
1.24	228	260	282	297	305	309	308	305	299	293	286	279	272	266	261	257
1.26	229	261	283	297	305	308	308	304	299	293	287	280	274	268	263	258
1.28	230	261	283	297	305	308	307	304	299	293	287	281	275	270	264	260
1.30	231	262	283	297	304	307	306	303	299	294	288	282	277	271	266	261
1.32	232	263	284	297	304	307	306	303	299	294	289	283	278	273	267	262
1.34	232	263	284	297	304	306	305	302	298	294	289	284	279	274	269	264
1.36	233	264	285	297	303	305	304	302	298	294	290	285	281	276	271	265
1.38	234	265	285	297	303	305	304	301	297	294	290	286	282	277	272	266
1.40	235	266	285	297	303	304	303	300	297	294	291	287	283	279	273	268
1.42	236	266	286	297	302	304	302	300	297	294	291	288	284	280	275	269
1.44	237	267	286	297	302	303	301	299	296	294	291	289	286	281	276	270
1.46	237	267	286	297	302	302	301	298	296	294	292	289	287	283	277	271
1.48	238	268	286	297	301	302	300	298	295	293	292	290	287	284	279	272
1.50	238	268	286	297	301	301	299	297	295	293	292	290	288	285	280	273

Table 4. Accuracy of position of the primary of a double star with magnitudes $V_1 = 10$ and $V_2 = 11$ and projected separation (along scan) equal to one half the grid period. The colours are $C_1 = C_2 = 0.0$.

GRID PER. (")	DELTA															
	.08	.11	.14	.17	.20	.23	.26	.29	.32	.35	.38	.41	.44	.47	.50	.53
.50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.52	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.54	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.58	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.60	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
.62	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	0	0
.64	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	4	3	2	2	1	0	1
.66	9	10	11	11	11	11	10	9	8	7	6	4	3	1	0	1
.68	15	17	18	19	19	18	17	16	14	12	10	7	5	2	0	2
.70	23	26	28	29	29	28	27	25	22	19	15	11	8	4	0	4
.72	34	39	41	43	43	42	39	36	32	27	22	17	11	5	0	5
.74	47	53	57	59	59	57	54	50	44	38	31	23	15	8	0	7
.76	62	70	75	77	78	76	72	66	59	50	41	31	20	10	0	9
.78	78	88	94	98	98	96	91	83	74	64	52	39	26	13	0	12
.80	95	107	115	119	120	117	111	103	92	79	64	48	32	16	0	15
.82	111	126	136	141	142	139	132	122	109	94	77	58	39	19	0	18
.84	127	144	156	162	163	160	153	142	127	110	90	68	46	23	0	21
.86	142	162	175	182	184	181	173	161	145	126	103	79	53	26	0	25
.88	155	176	191	199	202	199	192	179	162	141	116	89	60	30	1	28
.90	166	189	205	214	218	216	208	195	177	155	128	98	66	33	0	31
.92	175	199	216	227	231	230	223	210	191	168	140	108	73	36	1	35
.94	181	207	225	237	242	241	234	221	203	179	149	116	78	39	1	37
.96	187	213	232	245	250	250	243	231	212	188	157	122	83	42	1	40
.98	191	218	238	251	257	257	251	238	220	195	164	128	87	44	1	42
1.00	194	222	242	255	262	262	256	244	225	200	169	132	90	46	0	44
1.02	196	225	245	259	266	266	260	248	229	204	173	135	93	47	1	45
1.04	198	227	248	261	268	269	263	251	232	207	175	137	94	48	2	46
1.06	200	229	250	263	270	271	265	253	234	208	176	138	95	48	2	46
1.08	201	230	251	265	272	272	266	254	235	209	177	139	95	49	3	46
1.10	202	231	252	266	273	273	267	254	235	209	177	139	96	50		

Table 2. Same as Table 1 but for V = 10 and C = 0.5.

GRID PER. (")	DELTA															
	.08	.11	.14	.17	.20	.23	.26	.29	.32	.35	.38	.41	.44	.47	.50	.53
.40	51	60	67	72	77	81	84	86	88	88	89	88	87	85	83	80
.42	68	79	88	96	102	107	111	114	116	117	117	116	115	113	110	106
.44	84	98	109	119	126	133	138	141	144	145	145	145	143	140	136	132
.46	100	116	130	141	150	157	163	168	170	172	172	171	169	166	161	156
.48	114	133	148	161	171	180	186	191	194	196	196	195	193	189	184	178
.50	126	147	164	178	190	199	207	212	216	218	218	216	214	209	204	197
.52	137	159	178	193	206	216	224	230	234	236	236	234	231	227	221	213
.54	145	169	189	205	219	229	238	244	248	250	250	249	245	241	234	226
.56	152	177	198	215	228	240	248	255	259	261	262	260	256	251	245	236
.58	157	183	204	222	235	248	257	263	268	270	270	268	265	259	252	244
.60	161	187	209	226	241	253	262	269	273	276	276	274	270	265	258	249
.62	163	189	211	229	244	256	266	272	277	279	279	278	274	268	261	252
.64	164	190	213	231	246	258	267	274	279	281	281	279	276	270	263	254
.66	163	190	212	231	246	258	267	274	279	281	281	280	276	270	263	254
.68	162	189	211	229	244	256	266	273	277	280	280	278	275	269	262	253
.70	161	188	209	227	242	254	264	270	275	278	278	276	273	268	260	252
.72	159	185	207	225	239	251	261	268	272	275	275	274	270	265	258	250
.74	157	183	204	222	236	248	257	264	269	271	272	270	267	262	255	247
.76	155	181	202	219	233	245	254	261	265	267	068	267	263	259	252	244
.78	154	179	200	217	231	243	251	257	261	264	264	263	260	255	249	241
.80	153	178	198	215	228	239	248	254	258	260	260	259	256	251	245	238
.82	152	177	197	213	227	237	245	251	255	256	257	255	252	248	242	235
.84	153	177	197	213	226	236	243	248	252	253	253	252	249	244	239	232
.86	153	178	197	213	225	235	241	246	249	250	250	248	245	241	236	229
.88	155	179	198	214	225	234	241	245	247	248	247	245	242	238	233	227
.90	156	181	200	215	226	235	240	244	246	246	245	242	239	235	230	224
.92	158	183	202	217	228	236	241	244	245	244	242	240	236	232	227	222
.94	161	185	204	219	229	237	241	244	244	243	241	238	234	230	225	220
.96	163	188	207	221	231	238	242	244	243	242	239	236	232	227	223	218
.98	166	191	210	224	234	240	243	244	243	241	238	234	230	226	221	217
1.00	168	193	212	226	236	242	245	245	243	240	237	232	228	224	219	215
1.02	170	196	215	229	238	244	246	246	244	240	236	231	227	222	218	214
1.04	173	198	218	231	240	245	247	247	244	240	235	230	225	221	217	213
1.06	175	201	220	233	242	247	249	247	244	240	235	230	224	220	216	212
1.08	177	203	222	235	244	249	250	248	245	240	235	229	224	219	215	211
1.10	178	205	224	237	246	250	251	249	245	240	234	229	223	200	214	211
1.12	180	206	225	239	247	251	252	250	246	240	234	228	223	218	214	211
1.14	181	207	227	241	248	252	253	250	246	241	234	228	223	218	214	210
1.16	182	209	228	241	249	253	253	251	247	241	235	228	223	218	214	210
1.18	183	210	229	242	250	254	254	251	247	241	235	228	223	218	214	211
1.20	184	211	230	243	251	254	254	252	247	241	235	229	223	218	214	211
1.22	185	211	230	243	251	255	255	252	247	242	235	229	223	218	214	211
1.24	186	212	231	244	251	255	255	252	247	242	236	229	224	219	215	211
1.26	186	213	231	244	252	255	255	252	248	242	236	230	224	220	215	212
1.28	187	213	232	244	252	255	255	252	248	242	236	231	225	220	216	213
1.30	187	214	232	244	252	255	254	252	248	242	237	231	226	221	217	213
1.32	188	214	233	245	252	254	254	252	248	243	237	232	227	222	218	214
1.34	188	215	233	245	251	254	254	251	247	243	238	232	227	223	219	215
1.36	189	215	233	245	251	254	253	251	247	243	238	233	228	224	220	216
1.38	190	215	233	245	251	253	253	251	247	243	238	234	229	225	221	216
1.40	190	216	233	245	251	253	252	250	247	243	239	234	230	226	222	217
1.42	191	216	233	244	250	253	252	250	247	243	239	235	231	227	223	218
1.44	191	217	234	244	250	252	251	249	246	242	239	236	232	228	223	219
1.46	192	217	234	244	250	252	251	249	246	242	240	236	233	229	224	220
1.48	192	217	234	244	249	251	250	248	246	242	240	237	233	230	225	221
1.50	192	218	234	244	249	250	250	248	245	241	240	237	234	231	226	222

Table 5. Same as Table 4 but for colours C₁ = C₂ = 0.5.

GRID PER. (")	DELTA															
	.08	.11	.14	.17	.20	.23	.26	.29	.32	.35	.38	.41	.44	.47	.50	.53
.76	40	45	48	50	50	48	46	42	37	32	26	20	13	6	0	6
.78	50	57	61	63	63	61	58	54	48	41	33	25	17	8	0	8
.80	62	70	75	78	78	76	72	66	59	51	41	31	21	10	0	10
.82	74	84	90	93	94	91	87	80	72	61	50	38	25	12	0	12
.84	86	98	105	109	110	107	102	94	85	73	59	45	30	15	0	14
.86	98	111	120	125	126	123	118	109	98	84	69	52	35	17	0	16
.88	109	124	134	139	141	139	133	123	111	96	79	60	40	20	0	19
.90	119	135	147	153	155	153	147	137	124	107	88	67	45	22	1	21
.92	128	146	158	165	167	166	159	149	135	118	97	75	50	25	1	24
.94	135	154	167	175	178	177	171	160	146	127	106	81	55	27	1	26
.96	141	161	175	183	187	186	180	170	155	136	113	87	59	30	1	28
.98	146	166	181	190	194	194	188	178	163	143	120	93	63	31	1	30
1.00	149	171	186	196	200	200	194	184	169	149	125	97	66	33	0	31
1.02	153	175	190	200	205	205	200	189	174	154	129	100	68	34	1	33
1.04	155	178	194	204	209	209	204	193	178	158	132	103	70	35	0	34
1.06	157	180	196	207	212	212	207	196	181	160	135	105	72	36	1	34
1.08	159	182	199	209	214	214	209	199	183	162	136	106	73	37	2	35
1.10	161	184	201	211	216	216	211	200	184	163	137	107	74	38	1	35
1.12	162	186	202	213	218	217	212	201	185	164	138	108	74	39	3	36
1.14	164	187	203	214	219	218	213	202	185	164	138	108	75	40	3	37
1.16	165	188	204	215	219	219	213	202	185	164	138	108	75	41	4	37
1.18	165	189	205	215	220	219	213	201	185	163	137	108	76	43	6	38
1.20	166	190	206	216	220	219	212	200	184	162	137	108	76	45	8	39
1.22	167	190	206	216	220	218	211	199	183	161	136	107	77	46	10	40
1.24	167	190	206	215	219	217	210	198	181	160	135	107	78	48	12	42
1.26	168	191	206	215	218	216	209	196	180	159	134	107	79	50	15	43
1.28	168	191	206	214	217	215	207	194	178	157	133	107	80	52	18	44
1.30	168	191	206	214	216	213	205	192	176	155	132	107	81	53	21	46
1.32	169	191	205	213	215	211	203	190	173	154	131	107	82	55	24	47
1.34	169	191	205	212	213	209	200	187	171	152	130	1				

Table 3. Same as Table 1 but for V = 10 and C = 1.0.

GRID PER. (")	DELTA																
	.08	.11	.14	.17	.20	.23	.26	.29	.32	.35	.38	.41	.44	.47	.50	.53	.56
.40	22	26	29	31	33	35	36	37	38	38	38	38	37	37	36	34	33
.42	32	37	42	45	48	51	52	54	55	55	55	55	54	53	52	50	48
.44	43	50	56	61	65	68	71	73	74	75	75	74	73	72	70	68	65
.46	55	64	71	78	83	87	90	92	94	95	95	95	93	92	89	86	83
.48	67	78	87	94	100	105	109	112	114	115	115	115	113	111	108	105	100
.50	78	91	102	111	118	124	128	132	134	135	135	135	133	130	127	123	118
.52	89	104	116	120	134	141	146	150	153	154	154	153	151	148	144	140	134
.54	99	115	129	140	149	156	162	166	169	171	171	170	168	164	160	155	148
.56	107	125	140	152	161	169	176	180	183	185	185	184	182	178	173	168	161
.58	114	133	149	162	172	181	187	192	196	197	197	196	194	190	185	179	171
.60	120	140	157	170	181	190	197	200	206	207	208	206	204	200	194	188	180
.62	125	146	163	177	188	198	205	210	214	215	216	214	211	207	202	195	187
.64	129	150	168	182	194	203	211	216	220	222	222	220	218	213	207	200	192
.66	131	153	171	186	198	207	215	221	224	226	226	225	222	217	212	204	196
.68	133	155	173	188	200	210	217	223	227	229	229	228	224	220	214	207	198
.70	133	156	174	189	201	211	219	224	228	230	230	229	226	221	215	208	200
.72	133	156	174	189	201	211	219	224	228	230	230	229	226	221	215	208	200
.74	133	155	173	188	200	210	218	223	227	229	229	228	225	221	215	208	200
.76	132	153	171	186	198	208	216	222	225	227	228	226	224	219	213	206	198
.78	130	152	170	184	196	206	214	219	223	225	226	224	222	217	212	205	196
.80	129	150	167	182	194	203	211	217	220	222	223	222	219	215	209	203	195
.82	127	148	165	180	191	201	208	214	217	220	220	219	216	212	207	200	192
.84	126	146	163	177	189	198	205	211	214	216	217	216	213	209	204	198	190
.86	125	145	162	176	187	196	203	208	211	213	214	213	210	206	201	195	188
.88	124	144	160	174	185	194	200	205	209	210	211	209	207	203	199	193	186
.90	123	143	160	173	183	192	198	203	206	208	208	206	204	201	196	190	183
.92	123	143	159	172	182	191	197	201	204	205	205	204	201	198	193	188	181
.94	124	143	159	172	182	190	195	199	202	203	202	201	199	195	191	186	179
.96	124	144	160	172	182	189	195	198	200	201	200	199	196	193	189	184	178
.98	125	145	161	173	182	189	194	197	199	199	198	196	194	190	186	182	176
1.00	127	147	162	174	183	190	194	197	199	198	196	194	192	188	184	180	175
1.02	128	148	164	176	184	190	194	196	195	194	192	190	186	182	178	173	173
1.04	130	150	166	177	186	192	195	197	197	195	193	191	188	184	181	177	172
1.06	132	152	168	179	187	193	196	197	196	195	192	189	186	183	179	175	171
1.08	134	154	170	181	189	194	197	197	196	194	191	188	185	181	178	174	170
1.10	136	156	172	183	191	195	198	198	196	194	191	187	184	180	177	173	170
1.12	138	158	174	185	192	199	198	197	194	190	186	183	179	176	172	169	169
1.14	139	160	176	187	194	198	200	199	197	194	190	186	182	178	175	172	169
1.16	141	162	177	188	196	199	201	200	199	194	189	185	181	177	174	171	168
1.18	142	164	179	190	197	201	202	200	198	194	189	185	180	177	173	171	168
1.20	144	165	181	191	198	202	203	201	198	194	189	184	180	176	173	170	168
1.22	145	166	182	193	200	203	203	202	198	194	189	184	180	176	173	170	168
1.24	146	168	183	194	201	204	204	202	199	194	189	184	180	176	172	170	167
1.26	147	169	184	195	202	205	205	203	199	194	189	184	179	175	172	170	167
1.28	148	170	185	196	202	205	205	203	199	194	189	184	180	176	172	170	168
1.30	149	170	186	197	203	206	206	204	200	195	190	184	180	176	172	170	168
1.32	150	171	187	197	203	206	206	204	200	195	190	185	180	176	173	170	168
1.34	150	172	187	198	204	207	206	204	200	195	190	185	180	176	173	170	168
1.36	151	172	188	198	204	207	207	204	200	196	190	185	181	177	173	171	169
1.38	151	173	188	198	204	207	207	204	200	196	191	186	181	177	174	171	169
1.40	152	173	188	198	204	207	207	204	200	196	191	186	182	178	174	172	169
1.42	152	173	189	199	204	207	206	204	200	196	191	186	182	178	175	172	170
1.44	152	174	189	199	204	207	206	204	200	196	192	187	183	179	175	173	170
1.46	153	174	189	199	204	206	206	204	200	196	192	187	183	179	176	173	171
1.48	153	174	189	199	204	206	206	203	200	196	192	188	184	180	177	174	171
1.50	153	174	189	198	204	206	205	203	200	196	192	188	185	181	177	174	171

Table 6. Same as Table 4 but for colours $C_1 = C_2 = 1.0$.

GRID PER. (")	DELTA															
	.08	.11	.14	.17	.20	.23	.26	.29	.32	.35	.38	.41	.44	.47	.50	.53
.50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.52	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.54	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.58	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.62	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
.64	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
.66	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	0	0
.68	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	2	2	2	1	0	0
.70	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	4	3	2	2	1	0
.72	8	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	8	7	6	5	4	2	1	0
.74	11	12	13	14	14	13	13	12	10	9	7	5	4	2	1	0
.76	15	17	18	19	19	19	18	16	14	12	10	8	5	2	0	2
.78	21	23	25	26	26	25	24	22	19	17	14	10	7	3	0	3
.80	27	30	33	34	34	33	31	29	26	22	18	13	9	4	0	4
.82	34	39	42	43	43	42	40	37	33	28	23	17	11	6	0	5
.84	42	48	52	53	54	52	50	46	41	35	28	21	14	7	0	7
.86	51	58	62	65	65	63	60	55	50	42	35	26	17	9	0	8
.88	60	68	73	76	76	75	71	66	59	51	41	31	21	10	0	10
.90	69	78	84	87	88	86	82	76	68	59	48	36	24	12	0	11
.92	77	88	95	99	100	98	93	87	78	67	55	42	28	14	0	13
.94	85	97	105	109	110	108	104	97	87	75	62	47	32	16	0	15
.96	92	105	113	118	120	118	114	106	96	83	69	52	35	17	0	17
.98	98	112	121	127	129	127	123	115	104	90	75	57	38	19	0	18
1.00	103	118	128	134	136	135	130	122	111	97	80	62	41	21	0	20
1.02	108	123	134	140	143	142	137	129	117	103	85	65	44	22	0	21
1.04	112	127	139	145	148	147	143	134	122	107	89	69	46	23	1	22
1.06	115	131	143	150	153	152	147	139	127	111	93	72	48	24	1	23
1.08	118	134	146	153	157	156	151	143	130	115	96	74	50	25	1	24
1.10																

TABLE 2. Total transmittance of instrument: three mirrors, grid support plate, relay optics, and IDT window. Two options are admitted: ordinary glass optics (IGLASS = 1) or UV transparent fused quartz optics (IGLASS = 2). Glass optics is the baseline option.

λ (nm)	$T(\lambda)$	
	IGLASS = 1	IGLASS = 2
150	0	0
175	0	0.1
200	0	0.25
225	0	0.35
250	0	0.40
275	0	0.45
300	0	0.45
325	0.25	0.45
350	0.37	0.45
375	0.45	0.45
400	0.45	0.45
425	0.45	0.45
450	0.45	0.45
475	0.45	0.45
500	0.45	0.45
525	0.45	0.45
550	0.45	0.45
575	0.45	0.45
600	0.45	0.45
625	0.45	0.45
650	0.45	0.45
675	0.45	0.45
700	0.45	0.45
725	0.45	0.45
750	0.45	0.45
775	0.45	0.45
800	0.45	0.45
825	0.45	0.45
850	0.45	0.45
875	0.45	0.45

TABLE 3. Photocathode quantum efficiency. S20 is the baseline.

λ (nm)	$Q(\lambda)$	
	S20	Bialkali
150	0	0
175	0.2	0.18
200	0.25	0.19
225	0.25	0.19
250	0.25	0.19
275	0.25	0.20
300	0.23	0.22
325	0.21	0.24
350	0.23	0.25
375	0.25	0.26
400	0.25	0.25
425	0.24	0.23
450	0.22	0.22
475	0.18	0.18
500	0.16	0.15
525	0.135	0.11
550	0.12	0.07
575	0.096	0.03
600	0.077	0.015
625	0.063	0.005
650	0.048	0
675	0.036	0
700	0.027	0
725	0.019	0
750	0.012	0
775	0.0075	0
800	0.004	0
825	0.0025	0
850	0.0012	0
875	0.0005	0

TABLE 1. Smearred monochromatic fluxes of mainsequence stars. The table gives $\lg(f_\lambda / 1 \text{ photon s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1})$ for unreddened $V = 0$ stars of different colours $(B - V)_0$. Compiled from O'Connell (1973), Willstrop (1964), and Jamar *et al.* (1976), using colours according to Schmidt-Kaler (1965). Fluxes for $(B - V)_0 > 0.5$ and $\lambda < 325 \text{ nm}$ were obtained by extrapolation.

λ (nm)	$(B - V)_0$							
	-0.25	0.00	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50
150	9.00	7.39	6.28	4.93	2.73	0.68	-1.82	-6.02
175	8.91	7.56	6.80	5.70	3.95	2.34	0.44	-2.86
200	8.86	7.63	7.12	6.09	4.13	3.60	2.10	-0.50
225	8.65	7.57	7.23	6.60	5.29	4.55	3.45	1.35
250	8.70	7.54	7.19	6.56	5.73	5.30	4.40	2.80
275	8.55	7.55	7.37	7.11	6.45	5.84	5.24	3.94
300	8.48	7.64	7.48	7.29	6.74	6.28	5.88	4.88
325	8.39	7.73	7.58	7.46	7.02	6.71	6.41	5.61
350	8.32	7.82	7.69	7.64	7.31	7.04	6.92	6.31
375	8.33	8.03	7.89	7.80	7.52	7.30	7.14	6.97
400	8.32	8.24	8.08	7.90	7.70	7.54	7.37	7.25
425	8.28	8.21	8.11	7.96	7.76	7.63	7.51	7.29
450	8.23	8.18	8.11	8.02	7.95	7.90	7.83	7.65
475	8.17	8.01	8.09	8.04	7.99	7.95	7.84	7.69
500	8.08	8.02	8.03	8.00	7.96	7.94	7.87	7.79
525	8.05	7.99	8.03	8.03	7.97	7.95	7.92	7.90
550	8.00	8.01	8.02	8.02	8.03	8.06	8.06	8.04
575	7.95	7.97	8.00	8.01	8.04	8.09	8.12	8.10
600	7.91	7.93	7.97	7.99	8.02	8.06	8.09	8.04
625	7.85	7.90	7.95	7.99	8.04	8.11	8.16	8.09
650	7.81	7.86	7.93	7.98	8.03	8.11	8.18	8.24
675	7.77	7.84	7.91	7.98	8.04	8.13	8.20	8.33
700	7.73	7.81	7.89	7.97	8.04	8.14	8.23	8.42
725	7.69	7.76	7.86	7.95	8.02	8.12	8.23	8.44
750	7.66	7.75	7.85	7.94	8.02	8.13	8.25	8.56
775	7.62	7.72	7.83	7.92	8.01	8.12	8.25	8.59
800	7.59	7.68	7.80	7.90	8.01	8.12	8.26	8.62
825	7.58	7.66	7.80	7.90	8.01	8.13	8.25	8.62
850	7.53	7.62	7.76	7.86	7.98	8.10	8.25	8.64
875	7.50	7.63	7.76	7.85	7.98	8.10	8.25	8.65